

Perception of Qualitative and Quantitative Research Approaches in Mass Communication among the Postgraduate Students of University of Benin

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Abstract

This study explored the perceptions of postgraduate students towards qualitative and quantitative research methods in the field of mass communication at the University of Benin. The rationale for this study lies in understanding how the students view and apply these two approaches in their research, given the evolving landscape of mass communication studies and the increasing importance of both methods. The primary objectives were to examine postgraduate students' attitudes towards these research methods, identify the factors influencing their preferences and assess how these preferences shape their research practices. The study is grounded in expectancy value theory which posits that individuals' decisions are influenced by their expectations of outcomes and the value they place on those outcomes. A descriptive survey research design was employed and data were collected using structured questionnaire administered to 65 postgraduate students in the mass communication department using census sampling. The findings revealed that the majority of the students held positive or very positive attitudes toward both qualitative and quantitative research methods. Practical factors, such as resource availability and the nature of the research topic, were found to significantly influence their choice of research methods. Furthermore, students' perceptions of their preferred research methods influenced their data collection, analysis, and presentation practices, with qualitative methods being favoured for their flexibility in exploring complex issues. The study concludes that the choice of method is dependent on the choice of topic and sources of data. The study recommended that the university of Benin provide targeted training and workshops to help students gain a more balanced understanding of both methods.

Keywords: Postgraduate Students, Qualitative Approach, Quantitative Approach, Research Approaches, Mass Communication, Expectancy Value Theory

Introduction

Research methodologies play a crucial role in shaping the direction and credibility of academic inquiries, particularly in fields like mass communication, which often requires a blend of analytical rigour and interpretive depth. Among the numerous research approaches, qualitative and quantitative methodologies are the two most widely recognised and debated paradigms. These approaches differ in their philosophies, techniques and the types of data they prioritise. While quantitative research is rooted in the positivist tradition, emphasising measurable data and statistical analysis (Creswell, 2014), qualitative research draws from interpretivist perspectives, focusing on understanding social phenomena through detailed, often subjective, narratives (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

To begin with, postgraduate students in mass communication, as emerging scholars, are often required to make critical decisions about which research approach to adopt in their work. Understanding their perceptions of these methodologies is vital as it can influence their academic development, the nature of their research, and the knowledge they contribute to the field. More so, the growing importance of mass communication as a discipline underscores the need for postgraduate students to be well-versed in both qualitative and quantitative research methods. Scholars in the field recognise that both methodologies offer valuable insights, but the choice between them is often contingent on the research question, objectives, and the philosophical stance of the researcher (Neuman, 2014). While quantitative research provides the ability to generalise findings across larger populations and assess correlations between variables (Babbie, 2013), qualitative research allows for a deeper exploration of meanings, experiences and social contexts that might be overlooked in quantitative studies (Silverman, 2016). These differences are pivotal for postgraduate students in mass communication, as their research often addresses complex, dynamic and context-specific issues that may require an understanding of both individual experiences and broader trends (Bryman, 2016).

Nevertheless, despite the clear distinctions between these approaches, postgraduate students' perceptions of qualitative and quantitative research can be influenced by various factors, such as their academic background, prior exposure to research methodologies and the nature of their research interests (Mertens, 2014). This study, therefore, aims to explore the perceptions of postgraduate students in mass communication regarding the qualitative and quantitative research approaches. It seeks to understand their attitudes toward these methodologies, the factors influencing their preferences, and how these perceptions shape their research practices.

Statement of the Problem

The problem this study seeks to address is the limited understanding of postgraduate students' perceptions of qualitative and quantitative research approaches in mass communication. While both methodologies are fundamental to academic inquiry in the field, there is a lack of comprehensive insight into how students perceive these approaches, the factors influencing their preferences, and how such perceptions impact

their research decisions. This gap in knowledge is significant as it may affect the quality and direction of research in mass communication, where methodological choices are crucial for addressing complex issues such as media effects, audience behaviour and communication strategies. This study, therefore, sought to find out the attitudes and preferences of postgraduate students' toward qualitative and quantitative methods in their research endeavours.

Research Objectives

This study sought to:

1. Understand University of Benin postgraduates' attitudes towards qualitative and quantitative approaches in mass communication
2. Find out the factors influencing University of Benin postgraduates' preferences towards qualitative and quantitative approaches in mass communication.
3. Establish how these perceptions shape the research practices of University of Benin mass communication postgraduates.

Theoretical Framework

Expectancy Value Theory

Expectancy value theory is a well-established framework for understanding human behaviour, particularly in the context of decision-making and motivation. Developed by Fishbein & Ajzen (1975), expectancy value theory posits that individuals make decisions based on their expectations of achieving certain outcomes and the value they place on these outcomes. At the core of expectancy value theory is the idea that individuals' choices are driven by two key factors: expectancy and value (Eccles, Adler, Futterman, Goff, Kaczala, Meece & Midgley, 2002). Expectancy refers to an individual's belief about the likelihood of achieving a particular outcome, such as the successful completion of a research project using a specific methodology. Value, on the other hand, reflects the importance an individual places on the potential outcomes associated with a particular decision or behavior (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002).

The expectancy value theory is based on the idea that individuals' behaviors are influenced by their expectations of achieving certain outcomes and the value they place on these outcomes. In the context of the present study, this theory could be applied to understand their preferences for qualitative versus quantitative research methodologies. If students expect that a particular approach (e.g., quantitative research) will lead to more successful or publishable research outcomes, they may value that approach more highly and be more likely to adopt it. Similarly, if they perceive qualitative research as offering deeper, more meaningful insights into communication practices, they may prioritise it over quantitative methods. The theory highlights how students' perceptions of the rewards and outcomes associated with each methodology shape their attitudes and choices.

Understanding Qualitative and Quantitative Research Approaches

Qualitative research is often defined as an exploratory approach that seeks to understand complex human experiences, behaviors, and social phenomena. This approach is typically concerned with the "how" and "why" of a subject rather than just the "what." It emphasises the need to capture the richness of human experiences, often through in-depth interviews, focus groups, or participant observation (Creswell, 2014). According to Denzin & Lincoln (2011), qualitative research is aimed at gaining insight into the meanings and interpretations that individuals or groups assign to social phenomena, thus providing a deeper understanding of the context in which the phenomena occur. In this approach, researchers gather rich, detailed data from participants and look for patterns, themes, or concepts that emerge naturally from the data, allowing theories to evolve from the findings rather than imposing predetermined frameworks (Charmaz, 2014). By using qualitative methods, researchers can generate new theories that reflect the evolving nature of media interactions and communication practices, offering fresh insights into contemporary communication challenges (McQuail, 2010).

On the other hand, quantitative research is typically defined as a systematic investigation that focuses on the measurement and analysis of variables in numerical form. It involves collecting and analysing data that can be quantified and subjected to statistical analysis to identify patterns, relationships, or differences between variables (Creswell, 2014). This research approach is particularly valuable for testing hypotheses, measuring the strength of relationships, or determining causal effects (Babbie, 2013). The emphasis on numerical data and statistical methods allows researchers to generalise findings to larger populations and make objective inferences. Quantitative research is often described as an empirical approach that relies on observable and measurable data. This research method is rooted in the collection of numerical data, which is then analysed using statistical techniques to test hypotheses and draw conclusions about the relationships between variables (Flick, 2014). The empirical nature of quantitative research allows researchers to focus on observable phenomena and test theories in real-world settings (Wimmer & Dominick, 2014). The strength of quantitative research lies in its ability to offer precise measurements and statistical generalisations that can inform policy or industry practices.

Major Types of Qualitative and Quantitative Research Approaches

Qualitative research approaches primarily focus on understanding phenomena from a holistic perspective. It explores the underlying reasons, motivations and perceptions that influence human behaviour. The major types of qualitative research include phenomenology, grounded theory, ethnography and case study; some of the types are:

- a. **Phenomenology:** This aims to describe and interpret individuals' lived experiences and the meanings they assign to those experiences (Creswell, 2013). Researchers adopting this approach aim to uncover the essence of human experiences by engaging deeply with participants.

b. **Grounded Theory:** This seeks to generate theories grounded in empirical data. Researchers collect and analyse data through a constant comparative method to construct a theory (Charmaz, 2014).

c. **Ethnography:** This approach, on the other hand, involves the study of cultures and communities through direct observation and immersion (Hammersley & Atkinson, 2007).

d. **Case Study:** Finally, case study research investigates a particular phenomenon within its real-life context, often focusing on a single case or a small number of cases (Yin, 2014).

On the other hand, quantitative research focuses on quantifying the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This approach is often used to test hypotheses, make predictions, or determine relationships between variables. Major types include experimental research, correlational research, descriptive (survey) research, and quasi-experimental research.

a. **Experimental Research:** This involves manipulating one variable to determine its effect on another, often in controlled environments (Creswell, 2014). It uses random assignment to eliminate biases and establish causality.

b. **Correlational Research:** This examines the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them (Field, 2013). This approach helps determine the strength and direction of associations.

c. **Descriptive (Survey) Research:** This is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon, providing a snapshot of the current state without influencing it (Singleton & Straits, 2010).

d. **Quasi-Experimental Research:** This shares similarities with experimental research but lacks random assignment. It is often used when randomisation is not feasible (Campbell & Stanley, 2015).

Attitudes towards Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches in Mass Communication

Postgraduate students in this field are frequently required to develop a nuanced understanding of both approaches, but their attitudes toward these methodologies can vary depending on their educational background, theoretical orientation, and research interests. In mass communication, understanding the attitudes of postgraduates toward these methods is critical because their perceptions can influence their methodological

choices, leading to significant consequences for their research outcomes (Babbie, 2013; Neuman, 2014).

Qualitative research in mass communication is often linked with interpretive frameworks that emphasise understanding human experiences and social contexts. Postgraduates who favour qualitative methods typically view them as offering rich, detailed insights into human behavior and social processes (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018). Qualitative research techniques such as interviews, focus groups and ethnographic observation allow researchers to explore the complexity of human experiences in a way that quantitative methods often cannot. Many postgraduates appreciate qualitative methods for their flexibility and ability to generate theories grounded in real-world phenomena (Silverman, 2016). According to Creswell (2014), qualitative approaches are particularly valued in mass communication because they allow for an exploration of media consumption patterns, the interpretation of symbolic meanings, and the understanding of audience perceptions that might be overlooked by purely numerical data.

However, despite their popularity, qualitative methods face criticism from postgraduates who value the perceived rigor and objectivity of quantitative approaches. The quantitative approach in mass communication typically involves the use of statistical tools and large-scale data analysis to examine relationships between variables. Postgraduates who favor quantitative methods often argue that they offer more generalisable and reliable results, providing an objective view of the population being studied (Neuman, 2014). Techniques like surveys and experiments allow researchers to identify patterns and correlations, contributing to the development of theories that can be empirically tested and validated (Babbie, 2013). The emphasis on replicability and large sample sizes makes quantitative research highly regarded by many in the academic community, particularly those interested in drawing conclusions that can be generalised across different populations.

The divide between qualitative and quantitative approaches is often a matter of preference, and postgraduates' attitudes are shaped by a combination of personal inclinations and institutional pressures. Some students may prefer qualitative approaches because they align with their own theoretical perspectives, which may emphasise constructivist or interpretivist views of reality. In contrast, others may feel more comfortable with quantitative methods due to their background in more traditional scientific disciplines or their belief in the objectivity of numbers (Berg, 2009). Furthermore, postgraduate students' attitudes toward these methods may also reflect the educational environment in which they are trained. For instance, programmes that emphasise practical skills in data collection and statistical analysis may foster a greater appreciation for quantitative approaches (Wimmer & Dominick, 2011).

Importantly, there is growing recognition of the complementary strengths of both approaches. In recent years, mixed-methods research, which combines qualitative and quantitative techniques, has gained popularity in mass communication studies (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2003). This approach allows researchers to leverage the strengths

of both methodologies to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under study. Postgraduates who are exposed to mixed-methods research often report that this approach offers a more holistic view of complex media phenomena by combining the numerical depth of quantitative research with the interpretive richness of qualitative data (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). As such, postgraduates' attitudes toward these approaches can evolve over time, particularly when they are encouraged to view qualitative and quantitative methods as mutually reinforcing rather than competing (Creswell, 2014).

The attitudes of postgraduate students towards qualitative and quantitative methods in mass communication are also influenced by the evolving landscape of media research. The rapid growth of digital media and the increasing availability of big data have led to a rise in quantitative approaches, particularly those focused on content analysis, social media metrics, and user behavior analytics. However, the same digital platforms also provide rich qualitative data in the form of user-generated content, online discussions, and multimedia content, encouraging postgraduates to incorporate both methodological approaches in their research (Lievrouw, 2011). This convergence of opportunities for both qualitative and quantitative research suggests that postgraduates' attitudes are not static, but rather dynamic and shaped by the changing nature of the field itself.

Therefore, postgraduate students' attitudes towards qualitative and quantitative approaches in mass communication reflect a range of personal, academic and disciplinary factors. While qualitative methods are appreciated for their depth and flexibility, quantitative approaches are valued for their rigour and generalisability.

Review of Empirical Studies

Tandoc, Lim & Ling (2018), *studied audience perceptions of news credibility on social media*. The objectives of the study were to examine how users assess the credibility of news they encounter on social media platforms, particularly Facebook. The study was anchored on the uses and gratifications theory and media dependency theory. The study focused on how audiences actively evaluate media content based on personal needs and social context. The research used a mixed-method approach involving quantitative survey of 500 social media users in Singapore and qualitative interviews with 20 participants to understand interpretation patterns. The findings revealed that participants often use source reputation and peer-sharing behaviour to judge credibility. News shared by trusted friends is perceived as more credible. The study suggested that social endorsements influence news credibility more than institutional sourcing.

Another study by Boykoff & Boykoff (2007) analysed framing climate change: A comparative study of media coverage in the US and UK. The objectives of their study were to analyse how mainstream media in the US and UK frame climate change and whether these frames reflect or distort scientific consensus. The study content analysed 600 articles from top newspapers (*The New York Times*, *Washington Post*, *The Times* [UK]

and *The Guardian*) from 2003 to 2006. Findings revealed that; US media presented climate change with more balance bias, giving equal space to skeptics and scientists. UK media showed a higher alignment with scientific consensus, reducing uncertainty frames. The study concluded that national political culture influences media framing more than scientific evidence alone.

Another perspective was that of Uche & Okoro (2013) who studied the representation of gender roles in television advertisements: a content analysis of Nigerian media. The objectives were to investigate how gender roles are portrayed in Nigerian television advertisements. The work was anchored on cultivation theory and feminist media theory, focusing on how long-term exposure to TV content influences perceptions of gender norms. The researchers used content analysis of 150 television advertisements aired on Nigerian stations (NTA, Channels, AIT) over three months. Coded variables included: role (professional/domestic), product type, voiceover gender and physical representation. Findings revealed that women were predominantly shown in domestic roles and in advertisements for beauty or home products. Men were associated with authority, finance and technology. Male voiceovers dominated, indicating implicit gender hierarchy. The study found that media reinforces traditional gender stereotypes.

Methodology

A survey method was utilised, with a structured questionnaire serving as the primary data collection tool. This approach was selected because it facilitates effective sampling of the target population. Asemah, Gujbawu, Ekharefo & Okpanachi (2022) highlighted that survey research is particularly effective in examining people's beliefs, opinions, attitudes, motivations and behaviours. The study focused on postgraduate students in the Department of Mass Communication at the University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria, with a total population of 65 students, as indicated by available data. Census sampling was employed to distribute the questionnaire to all the respondents. Asemah *et al* (2022) explained that this sampling technique is ideal for smaller populations, typically 200 or fewer, making it appropriate for this study with its 65 participants. The simple random sampling technique was used to ensure equal chances of selection for each respondent. A total of 65 copies of questionnaire were distributed in person, achieving a 100% response rate. Data analysis was conducted using simple percentages, frequency counts and mean scores, with the results presented in tables.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Attitudes of Postgraduate Students to Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very negative	3	4.62
Negative	7	10.77

Neutral	15	23.08
Positive	25	38.46
Very positive	15	23.08
Total	65	100%

The data reflect a generally positive attitude towards both qualitative and quantitative research approaches among the postgraduate students. This suggests that most students are open to these methodologies. However, there is a smaller percentage who hold negative or very negative views, indicating that a minority of students may find these approaches less appealing or applicable.

Table 2: Views of Postgraduates on for Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methods

Statements	S.A (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean (X)
I believe that quantitative research methods are more effective than qualitative methods in mass communication studies.	14 (22%)	14 (22%)	15 (23%)	12 (18%)	10 (15%)	3.03
I find qualitative research methods to be more flexible and suited for exploring complex issues in mass communication.	12 (18%)	15 (23%)	18 (27%)	13 (19%)	9 (13%)	2.96

The data in this table highlights a balanced but slightly divided view regarding the effectiveness and flexibility of qualitative and quantitative methods. This suggests that while there is recognition of the potential strengths of both methods, a clear preference or consensus on one over the other is not apparent.

Table 3: Factors Influencing Postgraduates' Preferences towards Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches in Mass Communication

Statements	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean (X)
The availability of data and resources (e.g., time, funding, equipment) strongly influences my choice between	18 (27%)	16 (25%)	14 (22%)	10 (15%)	7 (11%)	3.42

<p>qualitative and quantitative research methods.</p> <p>I prefer qualitative methods because they allow me to gain a deeper understanding of participants' views and experiences in mass communication.</p>	<p>13 (20%) 17 (26%) 18 (27%) 12 (18%) 5 (8%)</p>	<p>3.13</p>
<p>The nature of my research topic (e.g., media trends, audience behavior) influences whether I choose a qualitative or quantitative approach.</p>	<p>19 (29%) 17 (26%) 12 (18%) 11 (17%) 6 (9%)</p>	<p>3.3</p>

The preferences for research methods are strongly influenced by several factors, including available resources and the nature of the research topic. This suggests that the choice of method is not purely theoretical but is shaped by external, practical factors and the research context.

Table 4: Perceptions shape the Research Practices of the Mass Communication Postgraduate Students

Statements	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean (X)
<p>My preferred research method (qualitative or quantitative) determines the types of data collection methods I use (e.g., surveys, interviews, content analysis).</p>	8 (12%)	11 (17%)	14 (22%)	7 (26%)	15 (23%)	3.28
<p>The choice of research method influences the way I analyse and interpret data in my mass communication studies.</p>	7 (11%)	12 (18%)	16 (25%)	17 (26%)	13 (20%)	3.19
<p>My perception of qualitative and quantitative research</p>	14	17 (26%)	18 (28%)	10 (15%)	6 (9%)	3.33

methods affects how I present (22%)
my research findings in
academic papers and reports.

The data here reveal that students' preferred research methods strongly influence their research practices. This demonstrates that methodological preferences extend beyond data collection to influence the overall research process, including how findings are presented. Thus, students' perceptions of qualitative and quantitative research methods have a profound impact on both the conduct and presentation of their research.

Discussion of Findings

For research objective one, which sought to understand University of Benin postgraduate students' attitudes towards qualitative and quantitative approaches in mass communication, tables 1 and 2 answered the research question. In table 1, the data imply that a large majority of postgraduate students view both qualitative and quantitative research methods positively, with majority (60%) expressing either a positive or very positive attitude towards these methodologies. This suggests a broad acceptance and appreciation for these approaches in their academic work. However, the presence of some students (15.39%) who hold negative or very negative views indicates that there are still some reservations or criticisms of these research methods. This minority might be facing challenges in applying these methods or perceiving them as less relevant to their specific academic or research goals. In table 2, the data suggest that postgraduate students are divided in their views on the effectiveness and flexibility of quantitative and qualitative methods in mass communication studies. While the majority views quantitative research as effective in mass communication (44% expressing agreement) which implies that quantitative methods may not be universally considered the best for all types of mass communication research. This could reflect a concern that quantitative methods, often seen as more structured, may not adequately address the nuances and complexities of communication studies, which could require more in-depth, flexible approaches. On the other hand, the question regarding qualitative methods being more flexible and suited to exploring complex issues in mass communication shows that while many students appreciate the exploratory nature of qualitative research (41% agreement), a substantial group (32%) either disagrees or remains neutral, indicating some uncertainty or skepticism about the ability of qualitative methods to address the complexities of communication topics in a systematic way. The fairly neutral positions suggest that while students recognise the strengths of both methods, they may still be unsure about which is the best approach or how to effectively combine them.

This aligns with expectancy value theory, as students are likely to expect positive academic outcomes from using either research method, such as high-quality research or better academic performance. The relatively small percentage of negative views could suggest that some students perceive less value in these methods for their research goals or anticipate challenges in effectively applying them. The neutral group reflects individuals

who are uncertain about the expected benefits of using either method, possibly due to a lack of understanding or prior experience, thus reducing their perceived value of either approach.

For research objective two, which seek to find out the factors influencing University of Benin postgraduate students' preferences towards qualitative and quantitative approaches in mass communication, Table 3 answered the research question. The data from table 3 highlights that postgraduate students' preferences for qualitative and quantitative methods are largely shaped by practical considerations, such as available resources (time, funding and equipment) and the nature of the research topic. With majority of students (52%) agreeing that data availability and resources play a major role in determining their method choice, it is clear that practical constraints significantly influence research decisions. This reflects a pragmatic approach, where students may feel forced to choose a method based on the resources at their disposal rather than a purely theoretical or academic preference. The importance of the research topic is also a key factor, with nearly 55% of students agreeing that the nature of their research influences their method choice. For example, a study focused on audience behaviour or media trends may be better suited to a quantitative approach, while a topic exploring individual experiences or perceptions might benefit from a qualitative approach. This highlights the flexibility required by students, as they must tailor their research methods to both the available resources and the specific demands of their research focus. The data also reveal that many students prefer qualitative methods (46%) when they are seeking deeper insights into participant experiences, suggesting that when the research aims to uncover meanings or personal perspectives, qualitative approaches are viewed as more appropriate.

This reflects how practical factors influence the selection of research methods, which ties into EVT's concept of outcome expectations. The fact that 52% of students say resource availability strongly influences their choice indicates that they weigh the expected benefits (successful research, academic outcomes) against the constraints they face (limited funding, time or equipment). If students expect that the necessary resources will be available to support a certain method, they are more likely to assign a higher value to that approach and use it. Similarly, the preference for qualitative methods when aiming to gain deeper insights into participants' experiences shows that students expect richer, more valuable findings from qualitative research in certain contexts, which in turn makes them more likely to choose it. Students' perception that the research topic influences their method choice suggests they anticipate different outcomes based on the topic at hand. For example, if the topic lends itself better to exploration (such as audience behaviour), students may value qualitative methods more, expecting deeper understanding.

Research objective 4 sought to ascertain how these perceptions shape the research practices of University of Benin mass communication postgraduate students. The data suggest that postgraduate students' perceptions of qualitative and quantitative methods directly influence their actual research practices, affecting their choices of data collection methods, analysis techniques and how they present their findings. The fact that nearly

50% of students agree that their research method choice influences the data collection methods they use (such as surveys, interviews or content analysis) implies that students see a strong connection between their methodological preference and the tools they choose for gathering data. For instance, students favouring quantitative methods might gravitate towards structured surveys, while those preferring qualitative methods may opt for open-ended interviews or focus groups. The research method also impacts how students analyse and interpret their data, with 46% agreeing that their choice influences these processes. This suggests that their perception of qualitative and quantitative methods has a broader impact on their research approach, guiding not only how data is collected but also how it is processed and understood. Moreover, the data indicates that the method chosen shapes the way students present their research findings, with 48% acknowledging this effect. This could mean that students using qualitative methods might focus more on narrative, descriptive findings, while those using quantitative methods might emphasise statistical or numerical data in their reports. Overall, this data reinforces the idea that students' methodological preferences extend beyond just theory and are integral to shaping their overall research design, from data collection to final presentation. This highlights the crucial role that methodological perceptions play in influencing the entire research process.

The data here link directly to EVT in the sense that students' methodological preferences shape the entire research process, from data collection to presentation. Students who perceive qualitative methods as beneficial for exploring complex issues likely expect positive outcomes, such as deeper insights and more nuanced results, which aligns with the value they place on these methods. Their perception that these methods influence data collection techniques (e.g., interviews, surveys) suggests that they expect these tools to lead to more meaningful data that align with their research goals. Similarly, the influence of research methods on analysis and interpretation implies that students anticipate better alignment between their chosen method and their analytical techniques, thus increasing the value of the research process. The impact on how they present research findings further indicates that students' perceptions are informed by the expected rewards of clarity, depth, and audience engagement, based on the chosen method. Thus, EVT helps explain why students use particular methods: they expect that the chosen method will lead to more desirable, value-laden outcomes, influencing their entire research approach.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study on postgraduate students' attitudes towards qualitative and quantitative research methods highlights several key insights into how these methods are perceived and how they influence the research practices of students in the field of mass communication. In conclusion, the study underscores that postgraduate students are generally flexible and pragmatic in their approach to research methods, with their preferences being shaped by a combination of theoretical beliefs and practical constraints. Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

1. Institutions should provide more targeted training and workshops to help students understand the strengths and limitations of both qualitative and quantitative methods. This could help mitigate the negative or very negative views some students hold and further enhance their confidence in using both approaches effectively.
2. Faculty members should encourage a more balanced approach to research by emphasising the complementary nature of qualitative and quantitative methods, particularly in mass communication studies. This would help students see the potential for both methods to offer valuable insights, reducing the divide between those who favour one over the other.
3. Universities should ensure that postgraduate students have access to adequate resources, including funding, time and equipment, to support their choice of research methods. Offering grants or logistical support could help students overcome resource-related constraints that influence their methodological decisions, particularly for those favouring qualitative research.

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